

A High-Performance Open-Source Solution for Multiphase Fluid-Structure Interaction

Wendi Liu^{1,*}, Stephen M. Longshaw¹, Alex Skillen^{1,2}, David R. Emerson¹, Carmine Valente³ and Francesco Gambioli³

1. Scientific Computing Department, Science and Technology Facilities Council, Daresbury Laboratory, Warrington, UK.
2. Department of Mechanical Aerospace and Civil Engineering; School of Engineering, The University of Manchester, UK
3. Airbus Operations Ltd, Pegasus House, Aerospace Avenue, Filton, Bristol, U.K

* Corresponding author. Email: wendi.liu@stfc.ac.uk.

ABSTRACT

A multiphase FSI framework using only open-source software has been developed, utilising components able to run on high-performance computing platforms. A partitioned approach is employed, ensuring a separation of concerns (fluid, structure and coupling), allowing design flexibility and robustness while reducing future maintenance efforts. Multiphase FSI test cases have been simulated and compared with published results and show good agreement. Simulation of a model representing an elastic aircraft wing with a fluid (fuel) sloshing inside is presented. This demonstrates the ability of this multiphase FSI framework in simulating complex and challenging cases involving a free liquid surface.

KEYWORDS: Multiphase Simulation; Partitioned Fluid-Structure Interaction; Multi-physics Coupled Modelling; Wing fuel-tank sloshing.

INTRODUCTION

The interaction between multiphase flow and elastic structures is an important phenomenon in a wide range of scientific and engineering disciplines, such as an aircraft wing with sloshing fuel tank (Saltari *et al.* 2021; Gambioli *et al.* 2019; Mastroddi *et al.* 2019; Titurus *et al.* 2019; Mastroddi *et al.* 2020; Gambioli *et al.* 2020) and the impact of ocean waves on elastic ocean structures (Gomes *et al.* 2020). Accurately simulating multiphase fluid-structure interaction (FSI) can help reveal the mechanism behind important and complex real-world phenomena, allowing for important design considerations such as how to protect the elastic structure from fatigue or failure, or to make use of the phenomenon to achieve active/passive control of the system. There is significant demand to develop an efficient and open-source numerical tool for the investigation of this phenomenon. Due to the nonlinear, time-dependent and multi-physical nature of various multiphase FSI problems, a simulation tool that is both robust and highly scalable in parallel computing terms is challenging. There are notable commercial FSI solvers. However, few of them can achieve both numerical

robustness and high scalability while also being able to tackle multiphase multi-physics FSI problems. Commercial software, such as ANSYS (Rao 2003) and COMSOL (Curtis *et al.* 2013) are able to provide fully-coupled FSI simulations, but it can be challenging to run large parallel simulations using them. Martínez-Ferrer *et al.* (2018) established an FSI simulation tool using OpenFOAM. Both fluid and structure domains have been discretised with the Finite Volume method and solved by OpenFOAM and parallel execution with up to four CPU cores was tested. Integrating both fluid and structure domains into a single library with a code-specific data mapping method is a good way to model multi-physical problems with small numbers of physical domains. However, maintaining these codes and incrementally adding more physical domains is then onerous, especially when different domain types cannot be tackled using the same discretisation strategy.

In this study, we aim to establish a new parallel partitioned multiphase FSI simulation framework using only open-source codes. We adopt a partitioned approach, ensuring good use is made of existing open-source software while allowing design flexibility and reduced future maintenance efforts. For a partitioned approach, a stable and accurate coupling algorithm with good scalability and flexibility is required. There are a number of key coupling libraries that provide algorithms for FSI simulations, such as Comana (König *et al.* 2016), OpenFPCI (Hewitt *et al.* 2019), preCICE (Bungartz *et al.* 2016) and the Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) coupling library (Tang *et al.* 2015; Longshaw *et al.* 2020). The Comana code is not open-source and OpenFPCI is designed for coupling between specific codes. The open-source coupling library, preCICE, is designed for coupling between mesh-based domains and has been used for FSI problems. In this work, however, we employ the MUI library as the interface coupling tool between fluid and structure domains with the eventual goal of coupling both mesh and particle based CFD methods. It provides highly flexible domain couplings as it allows an arbitrary number of codes to communicate with one another via Message Passing Interface (MPI) communications using a cloud of points data (rather than a mesh), combined with high-order interpolation

schemes to facilitate data use between dissimilar methods or discretisations. MUI coupling utilities with FSI coupling algorithms have been developed to achieve a tight and stable coupling. OpenFOAM (Weller *et al.* 1998) and FEniCS (Alnæs *et al.* 2015) are adopted as the multiphase computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and computational structure mechanics (CSM) solvers, respectively.

Figure 1 Benchmark results for the parallel performance of MUI.

Figure 2 Schematic of the open-source framework with implicit FSI coupling scheme.

All three codes are equally important in this framework. Codes used here are known to perform well in high-performance computing (HPC) environments and are validated in their respective problem-domains (Skillen *et al.* 2018; Bnà *et al.* 2019; Hoffman *et al.* 2015). In our previous study, we observed good parallel performance for the MUI library on up to 9,000 MPI tasks for a synthetic problem with a similar communication pattern to that of FSI (Skillen *et al.* 2018). A series of benchmark tests on the MUI library have been carried out on the UK's national HPC system, ARCHER, showing the scope for scalability based purely on the communication overheads introduced by using MUI (Longshaw *et al.* 2019). Figure 1 shows the results of a 300 million cell to 300 million cell coupled case, with a simple 50/50 split of resources, this shows good parallel performance up to 12,000 MPI tasks. The performance of the framework has also been demonstrated in our

previous work (Liu *et al.* 2021b), which shows good scalability with a parallel efficiency of 68% for 1000 MPI tasks for FSI simulations.

In this paper, we demonstrate the performance of the established open-source multiphase FSI framework. The coupling scheme and governing equations of the framework are also provided. A series of test cases compared with published results are presented to show the accuracy of the framework alongside a more complex demonstration simulation in the form of a sloshing aeroplane wing case. Future work on the multiphase FSI framework is also identified.

OPEN-SOURCE MULTIPHASE FSI FRAMEWORK

Figure 2 shows the flow chart of the open-source multiphase FSI Framework (Liu *et al.* 2021a). The left-hand side is the multiphase CFD solver (OpenFOAM v6) for the fluid domain and the right-hand side is the CSM solver (FEniCS v2019.1.0) for the structural domain. The interface coupling tool (MUI v1.0) is in the middle.

Fluid Solver

The multiphase fluid solver *interFSIFoam* has been developed based on the standard OpenFOAM Volume of Fluid (VOF) solver *interFoam*. The *interFSIFoam* solver has the same core algorithms as *interFoam* for computation of the multiphase fluid domain in that it solves the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations with finite volume discretisation and using the VOF method to model the free surface. The continuity equation reads as (Tuković *et al.* 2018)

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{U}_s) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where ρ_f is the fluid density, \mathbf{U} is the fluid velocity. The momentum equation of a general fluid property ϕ over an arbitrary moving volume, which due to the structure deformation, is stated as (Jasak 2009; Tuković *et al.* 2018)

$$\frac{\partial \rho_f \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot [\mathbf{U} \cdot \rho_f (\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{U}_s)] = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\mu_f \nabla \mathbf{U}) + \mathbf{s}_\phi, \quad (2)$$

where t is the time, \mathbf{U}_s is the velocity of the surface S (i.e. the grid velocity), μ_f is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, and \mathbf{s}_ϕ is the source term that includes both surface tension and gravity in the *interFSIFoam* solver. The space conservation law of the Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) formulation that describes the relationship between the rate of change of V and the grid velocity \mathbf{U}_s with the unit normal \mathbf{n} pointing outward is defined as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_V dV - \oint_S \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{U}_s dS = 0. \quad (3)$$

It uses to close the momentum equation with arbitrary moving volume and is a built-in function of OpenFOAM (Jasak 2009). The VOF method is used to model the free-surface, in which the volume fraction γ is determined as

$$\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\gamma \mathbf{U}) = 0. \quad (4)$$

The $k - \varepsilon$ turbulence model with wall functions is used to tackle the turbulence effect for the sloshing wing case. Additional functionality of *interFSIFoam* compared with the default OpenFOAM solver are: Calculation of fluid forces in each cell located at the interface between the fluid and structure domains and then sending forces to the structural solver; Receiving the displacement of each cell that is located in the interface between the fluid and structure domains and moving the grid accordingly; Conducting sub-iterations for fluid-structure interaction at each time step.

Structural Solver

The structural solver is developed using the libraries provided by the FEniCS framework, with governing equations discretised via the finite element method. The elastodynamics formulation can be expressed in the form of a generalized n -DOF (degrees of freedom) harmonic oscillator (GHO) equation as

$$\mathbf{M} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{d}}{\partial t^2} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{F}(t), \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix and \mathbf{F} is external loading. The dissipation of the structure can be modelled by including a damping term to (5) as

$$\mathbf{M} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{d}}{\partial t^2} + \mathbf{C} \frac{\partial \mathbf{d}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{F}(t), \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the damping matrix. In the present in-house solver, the matrix is modelled based on Rayleigh damping as

$$\mathbf{C} = \alpha_m \mathbf{M} + \alpha_k \mathbf{K}, \quad (7)$$

where α_m and α_k are Rayleigh damping parameters. Combining (6) and (7) gives

$$\mathbf{M} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{d}}{\partial t^2} + (\alpha_m \mathbf{M} + \alpha_k \mathbf{K}) \frac{\partial \mathbf{d}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{F}(t), \quad (8)$$

The generalised- α method, which is an extension of the Newmark- β method (Newmark 1959) is used to achieve a second-order accuracy for the time stepping (Bleyer 2018; Erlicher *et al.* 2002). The generalised n -DOF harmonic oscillator equation is valid for small deformations of the structure.

Fluid-Structure Interaction

The MUI scientific code coupling library is used to create a coupling interface between CFD and CSM codes. The fluid and structural domains of a partitioned FSI approach are coupled by kinematic and dynamic conditions at the interface where the domains meet. The displacement of the fluid structure interface has to follow a kinematic condition in order to ensure consistency, while the fluid forces, or tractions, acting on the fluid structure interface have to follow the dynamic condition to ensure conservation. The kinematic condition read as (Slyngstad 2017):

$$\mathbf{d}_s = \mathbf{d}_f \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{d}_s and \mathbf{d}_f represent the displacement at the fluid-structure interface in the structure and fluid domains, respectively. The fluid forces or tractions acting on the fluid-structure interface have to follow the dynamic condition as (Tuković *et al.* 2018; Slyngstad 2017):

$$\sigma_s \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{t}_f \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{t}_f is the traction at the fluid-structure interface, which is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{t}_f = \sigma_f \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad (11)$$

The stress tensor at the interface, σ_f , which is calculated from the fluid domain with an incompressible Newtonian fluid is expressed as:

$$\sigma_f = -p\mathbf{I} + \tau \quad (12)$$

where p is the pressure forces and τ is the viscous component of the stress tensor that is calculated as:

$$\tau = \mu_f (\nabla \mathbf{U} + \nabla \mathbf{U}^T) \quad (13)$$

where, the transpose of matrix \mathbf{A} denoted as \mathbf{A}^T . The dynamic condition dictates that the forces acting on the fluid-structure interface have to be conserved between the two domains. This is achieved using the Radial Basis Function (RBF) spatial interpolation method that is implemented within the MUI library. At time step $t^{(n+1)} = t^n + \Delta t$ (where n is the number of time step) and sub-iteration $(k+1)$ (where k is the sub-iteration number), the fluid domain solves the multi-phase flow field to

obtain the fluid forces. In this implementation, the fluid forces at each cell of the fluid-structure interface are transferred to the structural domain using MPI through the MUI library. The structural domain fetches fluid forces and applies them as the right-hand side term of Eq (8). It then calculates the deformation of the structure and pushes this information back to the fluid solver, again using MUI. The stress of the structure is then updated. The displacements of the structure in each cell of the interface are transferred and applied to the fluid domain as a Dirichlet boundary condition. Both fluid and structure domains are moved to the next sub-iteration after the completion of these steps. Several such sub-iterations are needed within each time step until convergence is reached. Both Fixed Relaxation and Aitken's methods are employed here to achieve a tight coupling. The displacement of the structure at the $(k+1)$ th iteration, \mathbf{d}_{k+1} , under the fixed-point Gauss-Seidel iteration method could be expressed as

$$\mathbf{d}_{k+1} = \mathbf{d}_k + \omega_k \mathbf{R}_k, \quad (14)$$

where ω_k is the under-relaxation factor at the k^{th} iteration. The interface residual of the FSI coupling at the k^{th} iteration, \mathbf{R}_k , is determined as

$$\mathbf{R}_k = \mathbf{F}_s \circ \mathbf{F}_f(\mathbf{d}_k) - \mathbf{d}_k, \quad (15)$$

where the \mathbf{F}_s and \mathbf{F}_f are the interface operators for structure and fluid, respectively, $a \circ b$ denotes a composite function of a composed with b , i.e. $a(b(x))$. For a Fixed Relaxation, fixed-point Gauss-Seidel iteration method, the under-relaxation factor can be expressed as

$$\omega_k = \text{constant}, \quad (16)$$

while for the Aitken's fixed-point Gauss-Seidel iteration method, the under-relaxation factor is calculated as

$$\omega_k = -\omega_{k-1} \frac{(\mathbf{R}_{k-1})^T (\mathbf{R}_k - \mathbf{R}_{k-1})}{\|\mathbf{R}_k - \mathbf{R}_{k-1}\|^2}. \quad (17)$$

A constraint can be applied to the Aitken's method to make it stable as

$$\omega_k = \text{sgn}(\omega_k) \min(|\omega_k|, \omega_{max}), \quad (18)$$

where ω_{max} is the maximum value of the under relaxation factors between the 1st and the k^{th} iterations. The Fixed Relaxation method is easy to implement, requires less computational resources per sub-iteration, but has a slow convergence speed. The Aitken's method requires more computational resources per sub-iteration than the Fixed Relaxation method, but has a quick convergence speed (Tuković *et al.* 2018; Scheufele 2015). Both methods have been implemented here using the MUI library. Sub-iteration for FSI coupling is implemented in both solvers.

Figure 3 Displacement over time of the beam with tip load case.

Verification

Three test cases have been simulated and compared with published

results for each component and the whole open-source multiphase FSI framework, and are presented here.

Beam with Tip Load

To verify the in-house CSM solver, an elastic beam with a tip load is simulated. This comprises a cantilever beam, clamped at one end and free at the other, with a density of 2600kg/m^3 , Young's Modulus of $1.7 \times 10^7\text{Pa}$ and Poisson's Ratio of 0.3. An external force is applied to the free end in the negative y direction. The value of the force linearly increases to 500N between 0s and 7s . After 7s , the value of the external force is equal to zero. Figure 3 shows the instantaneous tip displacement of the beam. The difference between the present simulation and that of Slone *et al.* (2003) is less than 1%.

3-D Kleefsman's Dam Break

The Kleefsman's dam break case has been simulated using *interFSIFoam* with a $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model and wall functions. This is compared with Kleefsman *et al.* (2005). This case comprises a water tank of dimensions $3.22\text{m} \times 1.0\text{m} \times 1.0\text{m}$, with a water column of $1.228\text{m} \times 1.0\text{m} \times 0.55\text{m}$ located on the right-hand side of the tank. A rigid block of size $0.161\text{m} \times 0.403\text{m} \times 0.161\text{m}$ is placed inside the tank and has a 0.6635m gap between the left-hand side boundary and its left-hand wall. The centreline of the block coincides with the centreline of the water tank. Standard gravitational forces are applied to the fluid, which makes the water fall and hit the block. Eight million cells were adopted for the mesh. A snapshot of the simulation results at time instant of 0.56s is shown in Figure 4. A good agreement has been achieved compared with Figure 18 of Kleefsman *et al.* (2005).

Figure 4 Snapshot of 3-D Kleefsman's Dam Break simulation at 0.56s .

Figure 5 Pressure time history at the monitored point and compared with Kleefsman *et al.* (2005).

The time history of pressure at a specific measurement point ($0.8035, 0.0, 0.161$), located at the top surface of the block, was also measured. A comparison between the present numerical results and

those published by Kleefsman *et al.* (2005) of pressure measured at the same point is shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that the present numerical results match well with the experimental results.

2-D Roll-Tank with an Elastic Beam

A test case to verify the entire multiphase FSI framework has been simulated. This comprises a partially filled roll-tank with a clamped flexible beam in its centre. Results presented are compared directly with those already published. The test case is a two-dimensional roll-tank with an elastic beam fixed at its middle bottom (Idelsohn *et al.* 2008; Paik and Carrica 2014; Zhang *et al.* 2016). As shown in Figure 6, the height of the tank is 0.3445m and the width is 0.609m . The tank is filled with sunflower oil to a depth of 0.0574m . The oil has a density of 917kg/m^3 and kinematic viscosity of $5 \times 10^{-5}\text{m}^2/\text{s}$. The flexible beam is constructed of dielectric polyurethane resin, with a height of 0.0574m and width of 0.004m . The density of the beam is 1100kg/m^3 and has a Young's modulus of $6 \times 10^6\text{Pa}$. The roll motion of the tank follows a sinusoidal function, with an amplitude of 4° and frequency of 0.61Hz around the centre of the bottom of the tank.

Figure 6 Geometry and dimensions of the roll-tank case.

Figure 7 Fluid (blue) and structural (red) meshes of the roll-tank with a clamped elastic beam.

Figure 8 Results of the roll-tank with a clamped elastic beam case for the instantaneous displacement of the beam tip compared with published results (Idelsohn *et al.* 2008; Paik and Carrica 2014; Zhang *et al.* 2016).

As shown in Figure 7, a 2-D mesh with a structured grid has been generated for the fluid domain, this contains approximately 0.6 million cells. The structural domain employs 3075 DoFs on the flexible beam. The top boundary has a Dirichlet condition of $0m/s$ for velocity components with a fixed pressure of $0Pa$. All other boundaries are designated as non-slip walls. The results of the instantaneous displacement of the beam tip simulated by the present open-source multiphase FSI framework is shown in Figure 8 and compared with published results. Idelsohn *et al.* (2008) carried out both experimental and numerical simulations that were based on the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) method. Paik and Carrica (2014) used the Finite Difference Method (FDM) coupled with the Finite Element Method (FEM) for the simulation. Finally, Zhang *et al.* (2016) obtained the results by using a framework comprised of the Moving Particle Semi-Implicit (MPS) method coupled with FEM. It can be seen that the displacement calculated by the present framework is close to the published numerical results. There are, however, discrepancies between the present simulation and the experiment. This may be, in part, due to the effect of the gap between the flexible beam and the tank walls, which is about $0.0029m$ along the z -axis direction, and can't be captured by the present 2-D simulation. In addition, the results presented are symmetrical, but the experimental results have a bias in the positive displacement direction. Figure 9 shows results on the water phase contour at different time instants. Compared with Figure 5 of Idelsohn *et al.* (2008) and Figure 8 of Zhang *et al.* (2016), the elevation of the free surface calculated by the present framework is comparable with them both. The bubble cavity generated near the beam tip as the oil flows over the beam is reasonably close to that of Zhang *et al.* (2016), but notably was not obviously captured by the 3D experiment.

Figure 9 Water phase contour of the rolling tank with an elastic beam with a: $t = 0.92s$, b: $t = 1.40s$ and c: $t = 1.68s$.

SLOSHING WING SIMULATION

In this section, simulations designed to simulate sloshing aircraft wing tanks have been carried out to demonstrate the ability of the open-sourced multiphase FSI framework of solving challenging cases with industrial relevance.

Problem Description

A cantilevered steel hollow beam is used to represent an elastic aircraft wing. As shown in Figure 10, the length, height and width of the beam are $L_s = 12 m$, $H = 0.3 m$ and $W = 0.55 m$ along the x , y and z axes, respectively. The dimension of the beam is based on an airliner wing. The first bending frequency of the beam is approximately $2Hz$. In the present simulation, an idealised beam is used, in which the damping matrix, as shown in Eq (7), is set to zero and the gravitational force on the beam is ignored. A tank is embedded inside the beam and is closed

at the free end. This represents the fuel tank of the aircraft. The tank has the same height and width as the beam, while the length is $L_f = 3.5 m$. In a notable difference from the set-up of Gambioli *et al.* (2019), there is only one compartment in the water tank without any internal baffles. The tank is filled to 50%. The mass ratio between the beam and the fluid within the tank is 0.07. Gravitational acceleration is applied to the system in the negative y -direction. The density and dynamic viscosity of the fluid are $1000kg/m^3$ and $0.001(N \cdot s)/m^2$. The surface tension of the fluid is set to $0.0728 N/m$. An external load is uniformly applied to the upper $x - z$ surface in the negative y -axis direction between $0s$ and $0.5s$. The magnitude of the load increases linearly from $0N/m^2$ to a maximum value of $7576N/m^2$ at $0.5s$. After $0.5s$, the external load is removed to allow the beam to oscillate freely.

Figure 10 Schematic of the sloshing aircraft wing.

Numerical Setup

The behaviour of the cantilever beam and the fluid inside the tank are modelled by the CSM and CFD parts of the multiphase FSI framework, respectively. Two sets of meshes are needed for these two domains. A quadratic Lagrange tetrahedral-based mesh is generated for the structure domain (Schneider *et al.* 2019), while a hexahedral-based structured mesh is generated for the fluid domain. After a set of mesh sensitivity tests, 12.7 thousand DOFs and 12 million cells were adopted for the CSM and CFD meshes respectively. A time step size of $0.0005s$ was adopted to ensure the Courant number remains below 1.

Figure 11 A typical l^2 -norm of R_k and under relaxation factor of the sloshing wing case.

Three simulations were run for the same case, each with different numerical complexity in the fluid domain. In the first simulation, a 2-D mesh for the fluid domain was used (i.e. one cell along the z -axis direction) and no turbulence model was used. The second simulation used the same 2-D mesh but adopted a $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model and wall functions for closure. The third simulation extends the 2-D mesh into a full 3-D mesh and employs the same $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model and wall functions for the fluid domain. Both 2-D and 3-D fluid meshes have the same topology in $x - y$ planes, but a different number of cells in the z -axis direction. The boundary condition of the non-slip wall is employed for all six boundaries of the 3-D turbulent simulation, while 2-D simulations only have four non-slip wall boundaries (two $x - z$ plane and two $y - z$ plane). The numerical settings for the structure domain remain the same for all simulations, which a fixed boundary is set for the

$x = 0m$ plane for the cantilevered beam. Aitken's method is employed to achieve a tight coupling between the fluid domain and the structure domain. After a series of tests, we found four FSI sub-iterations with initial $\omega_k = 0.8$ is suitable for this case. A typical l^2 -norm (Euclidean norm) of \mathbf{R}_k and under relaxation factor, determined by the Aitken's method as in Eq (17), is shown in Figure 11 from this simulation. As can be seen, the l^2 -norm of \mathbf{R}_k is below 10^{-3} after four FSI sub-iterations.

Results and Discussions

The displacement of the beam at $(12, 0.15, 0.275)$ is defined as the tip displacement (D). The non-dimensional tip displacements, D/H , for the three simulations have been presented in Figure 12. The non-dimensional tip displacements for the cantilever beam only (i.e. without the fuel tank) are presented in Figure 12 as a comparison. As can be seen from Figure 12, the beam bends downward and reaches $D/H = 0.529$ at $0.5s$ with the influence of the external load. After $0.5s$, the beam starts oscillating and the tip displacement of the beam follows a sinusoidal-like function.

Figure 12. Non-dimensional tip displacement of the beam.

Figure 13 Vertical fluid force coefficient of the water tank wall.

The instantaneous vertical fluid force coefficient of the fuel tank is also important to consider and is defined as

$$C_y = \frac{f_y}{\frac{1}{2} \rho_f u_{max}^2 L_f W}, \quad (19)$$

where, f_y is the forces along the y -axis direction from the fluid domain, which consists of the gradational force of the fluid and forces due to the sloshing phenomenon, u_{max} is the maximum oscillating velocity of the beam at $(12, 0.15, 0.275)$. The C_y value of the three simulations are shown in Figure 13. There are several small C_y spikes and one large C_y spike in each cycle of the beam oscillation.

2-D No Turbulence Model v.s 2-D Turbulent Results

The beam tip displacement of the 2-D no-turbulence-model case is quite

close to that of the 2-D turbulent case. The maximum difference between them is less than 0.1%. The instantaneous vertical fluid force coefficient of the 2-D no-turbulence-model simulation is slightly under-predicted compared with that of the 2-D turbulent simulation, especially when the vertical fluid force coefficient reaches the peak value at each oscillation, as shown in the subplot of Figure 13.

Figure 14 to Figure 17 shows the water phase contour of the three simulations at different time instants. At $t = 0.5s$ (Figure 14) and $t = 0.75s$ (Figure 15), both 2-D no-turbulence-model and 2-D turbulence simulations have the same free-surface profile. At $t = 1.0s$ (Figure 16) and $t = 1.65s$ (Figure 17), several numerical artefacts are clearly seen from the 2-D no-turbulence-model simulation compared with that of the 2-D $k - \epsilon$ simulation, which shows the importance of the turbulence equations on the simulation of the sloshing wing case.

Figure 14 Water phase contour at $t = 0.5s$ with a: 2-D no-turbulence-model simulation, b: 2-D turbulent simulation and c: 3-D turbulent simulation.

Figure 15 Water phase contour at $t = 0.75s$ with a: 2-D no-turbulence-model simulation, b: 2-D turbulent simulation and c: 3-D turbulent simulation.

2-D Turbulent v.s. 3-D Turbulent Results

The beam tip displacement of 3-D turbulent simulation shows a larger damping effect than that of the 2-D simulation. The instantaneous vertical fluid force coefficient of the 3-D simulation also has larger damping compared with that of the 2-D simulation. This is most likely

due to the interactions between the water and the front and back walls ($x - y$ plane boundaries), which cannot be captured in 2-D.

As can be seen from Figure 14 (c) and Figure 15 (c), the free surface profile doesn't change along the z -axis (i.e. no 3-D effect can be observed) for the 3-D turbulence results at $t = 0.5s$ and $t = 0.75s$. These free surface profiles have been captured by the 2-D turbulence simulations, as shown in Figure 14 (b) and Figure 15 (b). A clear 3-D effect with a concave shape of free surface can be observed from Figure 16 (c) and Figure 17 (c). The spatial-averaged water level at both $z = 0$ plane and $z = 0.55$ plane are larger than that of the $z = 0.275$ plane at $t = 1.0s$ and $t = 1.65s$. These 3-D effects cannot be captured using 2-D simulations.

Figure 16 Water phase contour at $t = 1.0s$ with a: 2-D no-turbulence-model simulation, b: 2-D turbulent simulation and c: 3-D turbulent simulation.

Figure 17 Water phase contour at $t = 1.65s$ with a: 2-D no-turbulence-model simulation, b: 2-D turbulent simulation and c: 3-D turbulent simulation.

Structure Domain on 3-D Turbulence Simulation

Apart from the results of the fluid domain, the FSI framework can also obtain displacement, stress and fluid traction profiles of the beam from the structure domain. Figure 18 (a) shows the displacement magnitude contour of the cantilevered beam at $t = 1.65s$. We can observe that the beam is dominated by the first bending mode from the displacement magnitude contour. The von-Mises stress is defined as

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} [(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + (\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2] + 3(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2)}, \quad (20)$$

where σ_{ij} is the Cauchy stress tensor. Figure 18 (b) shows the contour of the von-Mises stress of the beam at $t = 1.65s$. The clamped part of the beam has the largest von-Mises stress at this time instant. Figure 18 (c) shows the fluid traction contour of the beam at $t = 1.65s$.

Figure 18 Displacement magnitude (a), von-Mises stress (b) and fluid traction (c) contours of the beam at $t = 1.65s$.

Figure 19 Spectral analysis of D and Cy .

We also carried out a spectral analysis on the time history of the tip displacement of the beam as well as vertical force of fluid for the 3-D simulation and the cantilever beam only simulation, as shown in Figure 19. With the 50% filled water tank, the first bending frequency of the beam-tank system is smaller than that of the beam only. A high frequency signal (about $12.6 Hz$) also been observed by the spectral analysis of Cy .

CONCLUSIONS

We have developed a multiphase FSI framework by using open-source codes with a partitioned approach. The high-performance and open-source MUI coupling library is employed as the interface between fluid and structure domains. OpenFOAM and FEniCS are adopted as the multiphase CFD and CSM solvers, respectively. FSI coupling algorithms have been implemented using the MUI library to achieve a tight and stable coupling. Three test cases have been conducted and compared with published results in the Verification Section, which show good accuracy of the present multiphase FSI framework. A demonstrative simulation of sloshing in a simplified, beam-like aeroplane wing, has been presented in the Sloshing Wing Simulation Section and shows the ability of this framework for simulating complex and challenging cases. Ongoing work to further enhance the performance of the framework

towards an exascale FSI computing platform is currently underway, looking at aspects such as dynamic load-balancing on a per-solver basis, use of elastic HPC resource per-solver and the use of communication-minimising algorithms within the coupling layer operating separately from the solver parallelisation.

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